

Gold nanofilms at liquid-liquid interfaces: an emerging platform for redox electrocatalysis, nanoplasmonic sensors and electrovariable optics

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Abstract

The functionality of liquid-liquid interfaces formed between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES) can be markedly enhanced by modification with supramolecular assemblies or solid nanomaterials. The focus of this review is recent progress involving ITIES modified with floating assemblies of gold nanoparticles or “nanofilms”. Experimental methods to controllably modify liquid-liquid interfaces with gold nanofilms are detailed. Also, we outline an array of techniques to characterise these gold nanofilms in terms of their physiochemical properties (such as reflectivity, conductivity, catalytic activity or plasmonic properties) and physical interfacial properties (for example, interparticle spacing and immersion depth at the interface). The ability of floating gold nanofilms to impact a diverse range of fields is demonstrated: in particular redox electrocatalysis, surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) or surface plasmon resonance (SPR) based sensors, and electrovariable optical devices. Finally, perspectives on applications beyond the state-of-the-art are provided.

Keywords: Gold nanoparticles, nanofilms, interfaces, redox electrocatalysis, plasmonic properties

CONTENTS

1. Introduction
2. The interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES)
3. Functionalisation of liquid-liquid interfaces with floating gold nanofilms
 - 3.1. Thermodynamics of nanoparticles at the liquid-liquid interface
 - 3.2. Experimental strategies
 - 3.3. Electrovariable nanofilms
 - 3.4. The critical influences of interfacial AuNP immersion depth and interparticle spacing
4. Experimental techniques to characterise floating gold nanofilms
 - 4.1. Surface tension, capacitance and optical techniques
 - 4.2. Physical position and three-phase contact angle of the nanoparticles
 - 4.3. X-ray reflectivity and scattering
 - 4.4. Optical reflectivity and scattering
 - 4.5. Electrochemical techniques
 - 4.6. Summary
5. Applications of floating gold nanofilms
 - 5.1 Redox electrocatalysis
 - 5.2 Nanoplasmonics
 - 5.3 Optical applications
 - 5.4 Plasmonic photocatalysis
6. Perspective applications of floating gold nanofilms at the ITIES
 - 6.1. Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy
 - 6.2. Electrovariable optics
7. Conclusions and outlook

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Notes

Biographies

Acknowledgments

Abbreviations

References

1. INTRODUCTION

Liquid-liquid interfaces are emerging as powerful transparent, defect-free platforms for bottom-up self-assembly of ordered two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) nanoparticle (NP) arrays.¹⁻⁶ The fluidic nature of these interfaces allows them to self-heal, permitting the preparation of robust gold nanofilms of remarkable uniformity at room temperature, extending over large geometric areas (at least cm²), without the use of specialist equipment.⁷ The utilisation of liquid interfaces dates back to the beginning of the 20th century. Initially Ramsden,⁸ and shortly afterwards Pickering,⁹ discovered the stabilisation of emulsions, *i.e.*, interfaces between either two liquids or air and liquid, by particles. Those particles underwent assembly processes at liquid-liquid interfaces and, thus, stabilised emulsions in a similar manner to surfactants. Subsequently, such emulsions were called “Pickering emulsions”. However, the utility of this discovery remained dormant for several decades and was only revitalised upon the development of analytical methods capable of investigating the emulsions mechanisms of formation and intrinsic properties.

Since the turn of the 21st century, the spontaneous adsorption of micro- and nano-particles at either liquid-liquid or air-liquid interfaces,^{1,10-12} as well as the invention of practical methods of self-assembly,¹³⁻¹⁵ have been the subject of much scrutiny. Numerous industrial products and processes involve particles immobilised at “soft” interfaces such as antifoam formulations, crude oil emulsions, aerated foodstuffs and flotation. The immobilised particles act in many ways like traditional surfactant molecules, but they also offer distinct advantages. This research area is now

very versatile and multidisciplinary, combining fundamental science with large-scale industrial applications. The topic of colloidal particles at fluid-fluid interfaces has recently been comprehensively reviewed by Binks.¹⁶

Nanofilms consisting of conductive NPs, for example gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), are of significant interest both in terms of fundamental and applied research as they possess unique optical, conductive and catalytic properties. The manipulation of the physical positions^{17,18} and electrochemical activity^{19–21} of the AuNPs within the nanofilm is possible by controllably applying an electric field across an interface formed between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES).^{17,22} An ITIES may be formed between either aqueous-organic solvent,^{23,24} aqueous-superhydrophobic ionic liquid²⁵ or organic solvent-ionic liquid phases.²⁶ As ionic liquid-based ITIES have yet to be modified with gold nanofilms, this review will focus exclusively on aqueous-organic solvent ITIES.

In addition to floating nanofilms, it is well known that NPs can be assembled on solid supports as superlattices or superstructures.²⁷ This field has attracted tremendous interest over the past few decades, as highlighted by several recent reviews covering the synthesis, optical properties *etc.* of these superlattices.^{28–36} In the present review, we give a broad overview of the challenges inherent to self-assembling NPs at liquid-liquid interfaces, in particular with regard to AuNPs. We comprehensively summarise the methods currently available to study the physio-chemical properties of nanofilms both *in-situ* at the liquid-liquid interface and *ex-situ* after transfer of the nanofilms to solid substrates. We also compare the two approaches to nanofilm formation (liquid-liquid and solid-liquid) in order to help the reader understand the enormous breadth of this research field. However, the primary focus of this review is towards nanofilm functionalised liquid-liquid interfaces, and the review will not cover nanofilms at solid-liquid interfaces in-depth.

2. THE INTERFACE BETWEEN TWO IMMISCIBLE ELECTROLYTE SOLUTIONS (ITIES)

The meaning of the word “immiscible” in the abbreviation of ITIES is multifaceted. The ITIES is firstly immiscible in terms of the solvent molecules, resulting in a molecularly sharp interface but with a dynamic microscopic roughness as “fingers” of the aqueous phase protrude into the organic solvent and *vice versa*.³⁷ Secondly, the ITIES is immiscible in terms of partition of the electrolyte

ions between the two phases within a certain range of applied potential across the interface, known as the polarisable potential window (PPW). In truth most of the solvents are slightly miscible, *e.g.* the water concentration in 1,2-dichloroethane can be up to 110 mM.³⁸ Experiments are typically performed with mutually saturated solutions.

As the acronym ITIES suggests, both phases contain dissolved supporting electrolyte salts in either phase, enabling electrical conductivity. At a liquid-liquid interface the maximum upper and lower potentials are limited by the transfer of the supporting electrolyte ions. Thus, to obtain a wide PPW, highly hydrophilic inorganic salts (*e.g.*, Li₂SO₄, KCl, MgSO₄, *etc.*) are used in the aqueous phase and highly hydrophobic salts, typically composed of bulky organic ions such as bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium cations (BA⁺) and tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate anions (TB⁻) are employed in the organic phase. This means that at high positive potentials the PPW is limited by aqueous cation transfer, while at negative potentials the aqueous anion limits the potential window (see **Fig. 1**); whereas the organic phase electrolyte BA⁺ and TB⁻ contribute minimally.³⁹⁻⁴¹ Of course, supporting electrolyte of the organic phase can be chosen so that the ion transfer from the organic phase limits the potential window from one or both ends. For example, the replacement of TB⁻ with tetraphenylborate (TPB⁻) results in the positive end of the PPW being limited by transfer of TPB⁻ from organic to aqueous phase. A sufficiently polar organic solvent, typically 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE),⁴¹ 1,2-dichlorobenzene (DCB),^{42,43} or α,α,α -trifluorotoluene (TFT),⁴⁴ having relative permittivities (ϵ) of 10.4, 10.1, and 9.2,⁴⁵ respectively, is often required to facilitate dissociation of the organic electrolyte salt as well as to support the flow of current. However, even chloroform^{46,47} or toluene,⁴⁸ which have low values of ϵ (4.8 and 2.4, respectively), can be used at micro-interfaces, where the low conductivity of the organic solvent is not a significant issue. More polar water immiscible organic solvents have also been used, such as nitrobenzene ($\epsilon=34.8$).⁴⁹ Other highly polar organic solvents such as acetonitrile ($\epsilon = 36.6$)^{50,51} or propylene carbonate ($\epsilon = 66.1$)⁵² become immiscible with water if a heavy loading of supporting electrolyte is employed to force a phase separation. However, use of the latter two approaches results in a reduction in the overall size of the PPW. This is due to the fact that the solvation of ions is similar in both phases since the transfer energy of even highly hydrophilic and hydrophobic ions between phases is too close to 0 kJ mol⁻¹ to allow separation of the waves. As a result neither is suitable to form an ITIES with a usable PPW. The discussion above is not an exhaustive account

of all organic solvents used to form ITIES. For more options see the introduction of the article by Kasano *et al.*⁴⁸

The ITIES can be controllably polarised, or electrified, by application of a potential, either externally through the use of electrodes immersed in both phases or through a common ion dissolved in the organic and aqueous phases. The potential drop spans the interface and is termed the Galvani potential difference ($\phi_w - \phi_o = \Delta_o^w \phi$); it can be manipulated to provide a PPW as wide as ~ 1.0 V.^{23,24} The width of the PPW is limited by the above factors (choice of supporting electrolyte, solvent, *etc.*). A typical 4-electrode electrochemical cell used to polarise an ITIES externally is shown in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1. Electrochemistry at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES). Note the water phase is blue and oil phase is red in this scheme. **(A)** A typical cyclic voltammogram (CV) obtained by external polarisation of an ITIES using a potentiostat. At high positive potentials the polarisable potential window (PPW) is limited by aqueous cation transfer (*e.g.*, Li^+ , Na^+ or Mg^{2+}) while at negative potentials the aqueous anion limits (*e.g.*, Cl^- , or SO_4^{2-}). In theory, the PPW may be limited by transfer of organic cations and anions at positive and negative polarisations, respectively. This is indeed the case if moderately hydrophobic salts such as tetrabutylammonium tetraphenylborate (TBATPB) are dissolved in the oil phase. However, an extremely hydrophobic salt, such as BATB, dissolved in the oil phase contributes minimally. **(B)** A photo representing a typical 4-electrode electrochemical cell used to polarise an ITIES externally with two platinum (Pt) counter electrodes (CE), one in each phase, and two Ag/AgCl reference electrodes (RE), one in the aqueous phase and one in the organic reference solution (see the reviews listed in the text for more details on this solution). The dense halogenated solvent, in this

case α,α,α -trifluorotoluene (TFT), is on the bottom and coloured yellow as ferrocene is dissolved in it to clarify the position of the ITIES in the image.

According to molecular dynamics simulations and experiments, the liquid-liquid interface is molecularly sharp but rough, with fluctuation in the pico-second time scale of the thickness of ca. 1 nm for a water-DCE interface.⁵³⁻⁵⁶ If the majority of the potential drop takes place across this thin 1 nm interface, very strong electric fields can be achieved (ca. 10^9 V/m) for modest applied Galvani potential differences. However, the potential distribution within the interfacial layer is still poorly understood. Molecular dynamics simulations and X-ray reflectivity measurements indicate that both the liquid-liquid interface and the potential drop are almost molecularly sharp. For example, the electron density profile obtained from X-ray reflectivity shows a sharp change over a 0.2 nm distance,⁵⁷ and the electric potential difference from molecular dynamics simulations of a slab of water-DCE-water show a similar sharp decrease.⁵⁸ Girault *et al.* have estimated that ca. 30% of the potential drop is within the inner layer,⁵⁹ while Niu *et al.*⁶⁰ argued (based on earlier work by Schmickler⁶¹) that the potential drop at the interface is mostly at the electric double layer of the organic phase. However, Samec argued that this assumption is unjustified, as the potential drop is located at the nanoscopic interface.⁶² The structure of the liquid-liquid interface has been discussed by Dryfe.⁶³

A major distinguishing factor of electrochemistry at the ITIES is its sheer versatility in comparison to using solid electrodes, encompassing ion transfer (IT; **Fig. 2A-B**), facilitated ion transfer (FIT; **Fig. 2C**), interfacial electron transfer (IET; **Fig. 2D**) and photo-induced interfacial electron transfer (PIET; **Fig. 2E**) processes. In-depth discussions of the theoretical background and plethora of possible applications of electrochemistry at the ITIES beyond the scope of this review are available in a series of recent reviews.^{23,24,64-68}

Fig. 2. The versatility of electrochemistry at the ITIES. In each of the schemes the ITIES is polarised positively by a potentiostat. Positive polarisation of the ITIES can lead to ion transfer (IT) within the PPW of (A) cations from the oil phase (red) to water phase (blue) or (B) anions from oil to water. (C) For very hydrophilic cations, facilitated ion transfer (FIT) is achieved in the presence of a suitable ionophore species in the oil phase. Ionophores are complexing agents that shift the apparent solvation energy, and are typically used to facilitate the transfer of very hydrophilic species from water to oil within the PPW. Positive polarisation of the ITIES can provide (D) a thermodynamic driving force for interfacial electron transfer (IET) from a hydrophobic electron donor redox couple, *D*, to a hydrophilic electron acceptor redox couple, *A*. In some instances, more driving force is required to achieve electron transfer across the ITIES, and this can be provided by (E) harvesting solar energy using photosensitisers immobilised at the ITIES (*e.g.*, porphyrins or semiconductors) in a process known as photo-induced interfacial electron transfer (PIET). Negative polarisation of the ITIES may impede or reverse the direction of the charge transfer events described above.

3. FUNCTIONALISATION OF LIQUID-LIQUID INTERFACES WITH FLOATING GOLD NANOFILMS

In this section, we discuss experimental strategies to induce the adsorption of *pre-formed colloidal spherical AuNPs at planar 2-D liquid-liquid interfaces*. A comprehensive review of the adsorption of other nanomaterials at liquid-liquid interfaces (beyond the scope of this review), including both non-spherical nanomaterials, *e.g.*, 1D nanorods or 2D sheets, and Janus NPs was recently provided

by Booth and Dryfe.⁶⁹ Additionally, the electrodeposition of AuNPs at the ITIES has been reviewed by Dryfe *et al.*⁷⁰ The latter approach “decorates” the ITIES with AuNPs, though not to the extent that gold nanofilms of densely packed assemblies of uniformly arranged AuNPs are formed. Another topical review by Poltorak *et al.* comprehensively detailed both *in* and *ex situ* functionalisation of soft interfaces with molecules, nano-objects and nanopore arrays.⁷¹ Very recently, both Lee *et al.*⁷² and Binks¹⁶ provided thorough reviews on the applications of NPs adsorbed in 3D configurations at liquid-liquid interfaces (also beyond the scope of this review); forming either “liquid marbles” or colloidosomes. Liquid marbles are macroscopic 3D particle encapsulated liquid droplets with diameters in the millimetre to centimetre range.^{10,72,73} Colloidosomes are more than 1000-fold smaller than liquid marbles forming micrometre-sized particle stabilised Pickering emulsions.^{72,74} On the other hand, the formation of superlattices at solid-liquid interfaces has been thoroughly reviewed in the recent years by a number of different authors.^{28–35,75,76}

3.1. Thermodynamics of nanoparticles at the liquid-liquid interface

Several key studies have outlined in detail the various forces at play that dictate the adsorption of NPs at a liquid-liquid interface.^{13,14,77–80} In this regard, Flatté *et al.*⁸⁰ provided a particularly useful numerical model consisting of analytical equations that describe several key contributions to the total free energy of the biphasic system upon adsorption of NPs at the liquid-liquid interface. The key energies identified were (i) the energy of capillary forces, (ii) the energy devoted to changing the solvation sphere as the NP moves from an aqueous to organic environment, (iii) the line tension and (iv) the presence of an external electric field (applicable only for NPs adsorbed at an ITIES). Recently, Smirnov *et al.*⁵² created a very assessable calculator using Flatté *et al.*’s equations (available online in the supporting information of their article). The calculator describes the balance of the interfacial energies at a non-polarised liquid-liquid interface for NP adsorption as a function of NP size, dielectric constant of the organic solvent, surface charge of the NP, and three-phase contact angle of the NP (θ_0).

The main driving force entrapping a NP at a liquid-liquid interface is the capillary energy, *i.e.*, the energy a system gains if a NP occupies a portion of the interface. Primarily, the capillary energy is dictated by the interfacial tension ($\gamma_{w/o}$) and θ_0 (see **Fig. 3A** for a graphical representation of the

precise meaning of θ_0). On the other hand, the solvation energy acts as a barrier to NP adsorption. As a charged NP transfers from a more polar to less polar medium (so from water to oil), the contribution of the solvation energy to the overall energetic balance increases significantly, especially once the NP pierces the organic side of the interface. The line tension contains all kinds of interactions pushing NPs away from the interface; whereas an external electric field at an ITIES can be applied to forcibly entrap NPs at the interface (discussed *vide infra*).

A typical energetic profile of NP adsorption at a water-DCE interface is demonstrated in **Fig. 3B(i)**. On the aqueous side of the interface, approach of the NPs to the liquid-liquid interface is impeded by an energy barrier. As the NPs cannot reach the potential well that exists at the interface, no interfacial assembly of adsorbed NPs takes place. However, if $\gamma_{w/o}$ or θ_0 are tuned (for example by changing the organic solvent from DCE to propylene carbonate as shown in **Fig. 3B(ii)**), adsorption of NPs is facilitated. The latter is possible as the barrier on the aqueous side of the interface has lowered, increasing the likelihood of the NPs falling into the potential well at the interface and becoming trapped.^{7,52,81}

Once two or more AuNPs assemble at the liquid-liquid interface Coulombic repulsive and van der Waals attractive forces exert influence on the adsorbed AuNPs. Thus, the surface charge density (σ) of adsorbed AuNPs critically influences their tendency to adsorb and their equilibrium interfacial surface coverage.^{13,14,77,79} In the case of large particles (typically larger than 1 μ m), their weight and associated additional capillary forces need to be considered (not discussed herein).

Thus, all-in-all, three main strategies have been developed to induce AuNP adsorption at the interface by reducing the total free energy of the biphasic system either by manipulating: (i) electrostatics (*i.e.*, minimising Coulombic repulsion between interfacially adsorbed AuNPs by reducing screening effects, decreasing σ , or applying an electric field at the ITIES), (ii) hydrophobicities of adsorbed AuNPs (*i.e.*, affecting $\gamma_{NP/w}$, $\gamma_{NP/o}$ and θ_0 , see **Fig. 3A**), or (iii) interfacial tension (*i.e.*, decreasing $\gamma_{w/o}$). Also, simultaneously achieving a synergistic mix of more than one effect is common (*e.g.*, decreasing σ and bringing θ_0 closer to 90° with one strategy). Finally, as the adsorption of AuNPs is typically a kinetically controlled process dictated by the AuNP's Brownian motion,⁸² many of the strategies discussed involve emulsification or vigorous shaking of the biphasic systems to accelerate AuNP adsorption.

Fig. 3. Functionalisation of liquid-liquid interfaces with nanoparticles. (A) Schematic representation of the position of a AuNP at a liquid-liquid interface for a three-phase contact angle (θ_0) with the interface less than 90° (left), equal to 90° (center), and larger than 90° (right). θ_0 is defined as the angle between the water-oil interface and the NP-oil side of the tangent plane at the line of contact. $\gamma_{NP/w}$, $\gamma_{NP/o}$ and $\gamma_{w/o}$ are the interfacial energies of the NP-aqueous phase interface, NP-organic solvent interface, and water-organic solvent interface, respectively. The effective radius of the AuNP is r . (B) Contribution of the components of capillary forces (W_{cap} , red line), solvation energy (W_{solv} , blue line) and line tension (W_{line} , orange line) to the overall energy profile (W_{sum} , dashed black line) for a AuNP adsorbed at (i) a water-DCE interface ($\gamma_{w/o} \sim 30 \text{ mN/m}$) and (ii) a water-propylene carbonate (PC) interface ($\gamma_{w/o} \sim 3 \text{ mN/m}$). The excess of charge on the AuNP (Z_{AuNP}) was set to +400 and θ_0 was set to 88° . These calculations were carried out using Mathematica software and the CDF file is available in the supplementary information of Ref. ⁵². Adapted from Ref. ⁵² with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry. (C) On contact between an aqueous colloidal solution of AuNPs and an immiscible oil phase, a few AuNPs are

driven to the interface by the reduction of interfacial energy. However, the strong potential barrier on the aqueous side of the interface (seen at a distance of ~ 20 nm from the interface for the experimental conditions modelled with the dashed line for W_{sum} in **(B)(i)**) keeps most AuNPs dispersed in the aqueous phase. Thus, as shown in **C(ii)**, self-assembly of the AuNPs into a gold nanofilm under these conditions is not possible. On the contrary, the addition of promoters **C(i)** or modifiers **C(iii)** significantly reduce this potential barrier by providing charge screening, changing the AuNPs' surface charge density (σ), or synergistically modifying the AuNPs hydrophobicity (*i.e.*, affecting θ_0). Adapted with permission from Ref. ⁸². Copyright 2016 American Chemical Society.

3.2. Experimental strategies

Bell and co-workers^{2,82,83} have classified a series of chemically diverse molecules (*e.g.*, tetrabutylammonium nitrate and 4-tertbutylcalix[4]arene tetraethylester (Na^+) complex) that when introduced to a biphasic system act as electrostatic “promoters” of AuNP adsorption. A promoter must (i) contain a hydrophobic ion of opposite charge to the AuNP, (ii) not directly adsorb onto the AuNP (*i.e.*, displace the original stabilising ligand) and (iii) induce adsorption when present at low concentrations. Promoters induce adsorption by condensation of the hydrophobic ions on the organic side of the interface, thereby screening Coulombic repulsion acting on the portions of each AuNP submerged into the organic solvent,^{2,82,83} as shown in **Fig. 3C(i)**. The latter combined with the attractive van der Waals forces determines the interparticle separation distances at the interface. Both hydrophilic salts present at low (ppm) concentrations and amphiphilic salts with hydrophobic ions of identical charge to the AuNP reduce Coulombic repulsion only in the aqueous phase. Thus, neither can act as promoters. Nevertheless, Turek *et al.* demonstrated that by increasing the ionic strength in the aqueous phase by addition of salt, the reduction in Debye length at the surface of each AuNP can be sufficient to induce adsorption upon centrifugation.⁸⁴

A variety of methods have been introduced to reduce σ . Modification of AuNPs with stabilising ligands that terminate in carboxylic groups (*e.g.*, 3-mercaptopropionic acid, 4-mercaptopbenzoic acid, 16-mercaptohexadecanoic acid) allow effective modulation of σ by pH.^{79,85} Indeed, such a tactic was used to reversibly adsorb/desorb AuNPs <10 nm in size from the interface.⁸⁵ Another approach is to introduce “modifiers” to the biphasic system. As defined by Bell and co-workers,^{2,82} a modifier tunes σ , but also synergistically modifies the surface hydrophobicity of the AuNPs (*i.e.*, affecting θ_0). Unlike promoters, modifiers may coordinate with the initial ligand on the AuNP or substitute the ligand completely *in situ*, see **Fig. 3C(iii)**. Examples of modifiers include 1-

dodecanethiol,^{5,6} mercaptosuccinic acid in combination with tetraoctylammonium bromide,⁴ 2,2'-dithiobis[1-(2-bromo-2-methyl-propionyloxy)ethane] (DTBE),⁷⁸ poly-N-isopropylacrylamide (PNIPAM)⁸⁶ and tetrathiafulvalene.⁸¹

Arguably, the most widely used method of inducing interfacial AuNP adsorption is to introduce an alcohol, such as ethanol or methanol, to the biphasic system that simultaneously reduces σ and $\gamma_{w/o}$, ultimately allowing θ_0 to approach the optimal 90° .^{5-7,17,19,20,77-79,87-91} Alcohols may firstly reduce σ by competitive displacement of citrate ligands (*i.e.*, acting as modifiers).^{77,79} Additionally, water miscible alcohols will lower the dielectric constant of the aqueous phase as a function of alcohol content, thereby gradually decreasing σ .⁶ Experimental evidence⁹² and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations⁹³ indicate that the presence of a mutually miscible alcohol across both phases reduces $\gamma_{w/o}$. Indeed, gold nanofilms have also been successfully formed at pure aqueous-pentanol interfaces.⁹⁴ Also, the ITIES was modified using a minimum amount of methanol by initially suspending the citrate-stabilised AuNPs in a methanol solution, and then injecting this alcoholic colloidal solution directly at the ITIES using a micro-syringe,^{17,19,20,95} see **Fig. 4**. Such an approach was beneficial to prevent artifacts in ensuing electrochemical studies.

Fig. 4. Functionalisation of liquid-liquid interfaces with floating gold nanofilms by precise injection of AuNPs suspended in methanol at the interface. (A) Schematic of the capillary and syringe-pump setup used to settle AuNPs directly at the ITIES allowing precise control over the AuNP surface coverage. Examples of gold nanofilms prepared at flat water-TFT interfaces in 4-electrode electrochemical cells using AuNPs with mean diameters of (B) 12 nm and (C) 38 nm. Flat liquid-liquid interfaces were achieved by partial silanisation of the bottom half of the electrochemical cell glass walls. (D) Gold nanofilms were also prepared on larger curved soft interfaces using a 2 x 4 cm quartz cell. Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁰. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society.

Intensive mixing of immiscible biphasic systems of extremely low $\gamma_{w/o}$, such as the aqueous-propylene carbonate system ($\gamma_{w/o} = ca. 3 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$), can directly lead to gold nanofilm formation.⁹⁵ The disadvantage of using propylene carbonate, however, is its inability to form an electrified ITIES with a wide PPW; thereby, limiting its potential utility.

For solid-liquid interfaces, superlattice formation is governed by size, ligand effects⁹⁶ and chain length of the ligand.²⁹ A narrow size distribution is essential for increasing the degree of ordering in NP superlattices,²⁸ and this requires specialised synthetic methods such as digestive ripening.⁹⁷ The latter process is essentially a thermochemical step where a ligand exchange reaction induces the redistribution of atoms from polydisperse NPs, leading to a very narrow size distribution.⁹⁷ This method has been widely used for a long time, but the theoretical description of the process based on statistical thermodynamics was only developed recently.⁹⁸ The detailed understanding of superlattice formation at solid-liquid interfaces has yet to be replicated for the formation of nanofilms at liquid-liquid interfaces where, for example, higher flexibility of the interface makes the film more tolerant to defects.

Different strategies may be implemented to prepare nanocrystal superlattices at solid-liquid interfaces. One approach is to increase the concentration of nanocrystals by evaporating off the solvent.^{99–101} At a critical nanocrystal concentration, this leads to an entropy driven self-assembly phase transition to form an ordered superlattice known as the Kirkwood-Alder transition.^{102–104} Alternatively, the solvent composition may be altered to induce aggregation or self-assembly by decreasing the solubility of the nanocrystals.¹⁰⁵ The self-assembly of nanocrystals may be influenced by applying external stimuli such as electric, magnetic or electromagnetic fields.^{106–108} This can lead to a tilting of the orientation of anisotropic NPs.^{106–108} However, only recently have Yu *et al.* demonstrated the first use of an external stimuli, an electric field, to reversibly drive nanocrystal superlattice self-assembly.¹⁰⁹

Another interesting approach is the combination of liquid-liquid and solid-liquid methods for nanofilm formation. For example, the “drain to deposit” method, where NPs assembled at a liquid-liquid interface are drained to deposit the film on a solid substrate, allows tunable formation of large area NP films on solid substrates.^{95,110,111} Other examples include NP monolayer assembly by the Langmuir–Schaefer method¹¹² and by the three-phase self-assembly method.¹¹³ Additionally, bubbles (liquid-gas interfaces) can be employed for nanocrystal formation.¹¹⁴

3.3. Electrovariable nanofilms

Uniquely, an ITIES provides the additional ability to externally tune the electric field felt by AuNPs in close proximity to the interface. Thus, for negatively charged colloidal AuNPs in the aqueous phase, polarisation of the ITIES negatively (*i.e.*, the aqueous phase is negatively charged

with respect to the organic phase) will push the AuNPs towards the interface and potentially induce gold nanofilm formation (see **Fig. 5(A) left panel**). On the contrary, positive polarisation will repel the AuNPs from the interface, electrostatically dragging them back into the bulk aqueous phase and disassembling any formed gold nanofilm (see **Fig. 5(B) right panel**).

The voltage-induced reversible adsorption and desorption of NPs is dependent on their size and σ , and has been demonstrated for AuNPs < 2 nm in size^{18,115} and core-shell gold-silver NPs ca. 16 - 20 nm in size (but with a 4-fold increase in σ in comparison to pure AuNPs).¹¹⁶ However, AuNPs < 2 nm in size do not form lustrous gold nanofilms. Very recently, Montelongo *et al.*²² have shown that relatively large NPs can be assembled by the electric field at a water-DCE interface. In their study, AuNPs (16 nm in diameter) were functionalised with 12-mercaptododecanoic acid (MDDA) in order to protect them from aggregation by NaCl and TBATPB used as supporting electrolytes for the aqueous and organic phases, respectively. Nevertheless, it takes hours to induce assembly of such AuNPs into a lustrous film, although desorption of AuNPs from the interface can be performed in several minutes. Reversible electric-field driven formation of silver superlattices on solid electrodes has also been demonstrated recently,¹⁰⁹ so similar approaches can also be extended to solid-liquid interfaces.

Fig. 5. Electrovariable gold nanofilm formation by polarisation of the ITIES. (A) (Left panel) On application of a negative potential at the ITIES the negatively charged AuNPs are electrostatically “pushed” to the ITIES and form a gold nanofilm. (Right panel) On application of a positive potential at the ITIES the AuNPs are electrostatically “repelled” from the ITIES and the gold nanofilm disassembles. (B) Schematic of a demonstration device illustrating an electrovariable gold nanofilm in action by using a set-up with a coin facing the liquid mirror and a currency note at the back of the mirror. Reprinted by permission from Macmillan Publishers Ltd: Nature Materials, Ref. ²², copyright 2017. (C) Real images observed during the transition between a transmissive ‘window’ state (when no NPs are at the interface) to a reflective ‘mirror’ state (when NPs assemble densely at the interface). MDDA-functionalised gold NPs with 16 nm diameter were used and the ITIES consisted of an aqueous phase containing 10 mM NaCl and a DCE organic phase containing 10mM TBATPB electrolyte salt. Reprinted by permission from Macmillan Publishers Ltd: Nature Materials, Ref. ²², copyright 2017.

In comparison, lateral movement of larger AuNPs on the fluidic interface may be much more accessible. Bera *et al.* showed that the interparticle distance of interfacial adsorbed 2 nm AuNPs can be varied by as much as 1 nm by tuning $\Delta_0^w \phi$.¹⁸ Gschwend *et al.* demonstrated that changes in $\gamma_{w/o}$ in the presence of a surfactant as a function of $\Delta_0^w \phi$ can induce rapid lateral movement of

relatively large 12 nm AuNPs from one position on the ITIES to another, thereby behaving as “electrovariable Marangoni shutters” (discussed in Section 6.2).¹⁷

3.4 The critical influences of interfacial AuNP immersion depth and interparticle spacing

The immersion depth at the interface (*i.e.*, θ_0 values) may influence a AuNPs catalytic activity as an interfacial bipolar electrode (discussed in Section 5.1) by altering the ratio of surface area available for electron transfer reactions between the water and organic sides of the interface.²⁰ Additionally, the potential drop across the ITIES is not uniformly spread between the aqueous and organic back-to-back diffuse layers, although the exact potential distribution is not fully understood, as discussed in Section 2. Thus, the rate of electrochemical reactions taking place on the aqueous side of the interface may benefit from a greater proportion of the potential drop taking place there.

Charge transport along a gold nanofilm is achieved by multiple electron tunneling events (*i.e.*, electrons hopping between conductive AuNPs separated by a dielectric medium). The tunneling probability falls off exponentially with distance.¹¹⁷ The latter was demonstrated by Wuelfing *et al.*¹¹⁸ who observed an exponential decay of conductivity as a function of the thickness of an alkanethiol matrix separating gold monolayer protected cluster (MPC) cores cast onto interdigitated array electrodes (**Fig. 6A**). The MPC core separation distances in the film were easily varied by choice of the alkanethiol monolayer chain length.¹¹⁸ Thus, the extreme sensitivity of the tunneling probability to MPC core separation distances clearly highlights the need to precisely tune interparticle spacing to achieve truly conductive interfacial gold nanofilms. The latter would permit a massively increased cross-sectional area of reaction to facilitate IET by providing a continuous conductive interfacial route for electrons to travel from donor to acceptor molecules on either side of the interface. Thus, electrons injected anywhere on the gold nanofilm can be discharged at any point of contact on the opposite side of the interface. Support for the latter mechanism is evident from the significant increases in the rates of reaction for biphasic H₂ evolution and O₂ reduction due to redox electrocatalysis by interfacially adsorbed conductive bare or catalytic NP decorated carbon materials (*e.g.*, graphene or carbon nanotubes (CNTs)).^{119–124} The mechanism of redox electrocatalysis for these conductive carbon materials is explained in detail in a recent review,¹²⁵ and incorporates most of the elements of redox electrocatalysis by gold nanofilms described *vide infra* in Section 5.1.

Critically, for the performance of interfacial gold nanofilms as nanoplasmonic sensors, the strength of plasmon coupling, and associated “hot-spots” for SERS sensing, is dependent on the distance between the AuNPs.¹²⁶ Furthermore, Jain *et al.*^{127,128} demonstrated that as the interparticle gap decreases, the strengthening electric field causes a near-exponential increase in the sensitivity of the SPR frequency shift to the medium refractive-index (**Fig. 6B & C**).

With regard to electrovariable optics, theoretical^{129–134} and experimental^{7,90,135} studies have indicated that resonant light reflection, allowing gold nanofilms to act as nanoplasmonic mirrors, depends on the material of the NPs, their size and interfacial surface coverage (*i.e.*, average interparticle spacing should be substantially less than half the AuNP size¹). In this case, the immersion depth plays a minor role in determination of optical responses from a nanofilm. However, this parameter is crucial to facilitate electrovariable “on/off” behavior of nanoplasmonic mirrors. As discussed in Section 3.1, the deeper a NP is immersed at the liquid-liquid interface, the higher the energy needed to remove that NP from the interface.

Unfortunately, key factors that are beneficial for reflective interfacial gold mirror formation are diametrically opposed to facilitate electrovariable “on/off” behaviour. On the one hand, the AuNPs must be > 25 nm in size and suitably functionalised to have as low a σ as possible in order to achieve very dense packing at the interface. On the other hand, such large AuNPs are typically irreversibly trapped in a potential well at the liquid-liquid interface upon adsorption (considered in Section 3.1). An obvious approach is to increase σ causing an increase in the electrostatic driving force for desorption to overcome the trapping potential well. However, an increase in σ will also likely negate the formation of a dense gold nanofilm in the first instance. This problem has recently been partially solved by Montelongo *et al.*²² through using MDDA-functionalised AuNPs (high σ) and salt at moderate concentrations (screens Columbic repulsions between NPs in the film). Nevertheless, the assembly process took a long time and, thus, imaginative approaches to find the correct balance of opposing factors are still required to achieve rapid “on/off” electrovariable optics.

Fig. 6. Properties of nanofilms related to the interparticle gap. (A) The conductivity of gold monolayer protected cluster (MPC, specifically of $\text{Au}_{309}(\text{Cn})_{92}$) solid state films cast onto an interdigitated electrode surface decays exponentially as a function of the numbers of carbons in the alkanethiolate chain. The temperature of the measurements was either 70 (solid circle), 30 (hollow circle) or 60 (inverted solid triangle) °C. The inset schematically presents the interdigitation of monolayer chains in the solid-state MPC films. Adapted with permission from Ref. ¹¹⁸. Copyright 2000 American Chemical Society. (B) The LSPR maximum of a NP dimer (for polarisation along dimer axis) increases linearly with increasing refractive-index, similar to an isolated NP. However, the increase has a much higher slope for dimers with a smaller inter-NP gap. Adapted with permission from Ref. ¹²⁷. Copyright 2008 American Chemical Society. (C) A plot of the SPR sensitivity (*i.e.*, the slopes of the data plotted in (B)) *versus* the inter-NP gap (s , normalised by the NP diameter, D) clearly highlights that the SPR sensitivity to the medium

increases almost exponentially with decreasing interparticle gap. Adapted with permission from Ref. ¹²⁷. Copyright 2008 American Chemical Society.

4. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES TO CHARACTERISE FLOATING GOLD NANOFILMS

4.1. Surface tension, capacitance and optical techniques

Techniques that monitor the adsorption of AuNPs *in situ* are extremely useful, in particular when multiplexed with a 4-electrode electrochemical cell to track adsorption as a function of applied $\Delta_o^w \phi$. The voltage-induced reversible adsorption and desorption of AuNPs < 2 nm in size, noted earlier, was monitored by *quasi-elastic light scattering (QELS)*,^{18,115} see **Fig. 7A(i)** for a scheme of the experimental setup. QELS monitors the frequencies of capillary waves of a selected wavelength at the liquid-liquid interface spontaneously generated by thermal fluctuations. The resulting plots of $\gamma_{w/o}$ vs. $\Delta_o^w \phi$ are known as electrocapillary curves (**Fig. 7A(ii)**). In the presence of AuNPs the shape of an electrocapillary curve changes significantly, as shown in **Fig. 7A(ii)**, reflecting changes in the number density of AuNPs at the interface.

An alternative experimental approach to measure electrocapillary curves is *pendant drop tensiometry*.^{136–138} This technique has yet to be applied to monitor the adsorption of AuNPs as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$. Nevertheless, measurements of $\gamma_{w/o}$ for non-polarised water-decane interfaces in the presence of various adsorbed AuNPs clearly highlight the techniques suitability for future studies.^{139–141} Also, Hua *et al.*¹⁴² studied the adsorption of 5 nm AuNPs at the toluene–water interface using this method. The particles were functionalised with ion-pair ligands that promote absorption to, and desorption from, the interface.

Electrochemical capacitance measurements at the ITIES have highlighted an increased capacitance at negative potentials in the presence of either citrate-stabilised 16 nm AuNPs⁸⁸ or mercaptosuccinic acid-stabilised < 2nm AuNPs¹¹⁵. Due to their negatively charged stabilising ligands, the AuNPs are induced to adsorb at a negatively polarised ITIES and excess charge density builds at the interfacial boundary. Additionally, excess charge density may be attributable to interfacial corrugation in the presence of adsorbed AuNPs. Marinsecu *et al.*¹⁴³ developed a theoretical model to facilitate further development of such capacitance based characterisation of interfacial AuNP adsorption as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$, with experimental data closely matching the

theory (**Fig. 7B**). The non-linear optical technique *surface second harmonic generation (SSHG)* is a powerful surface specific technique that may be applied to the study of molecular species or solid nanomaterials adsorbed at the liquid-liquid interface,¹⁴⁴ see **Fig. 7C** for a scheme of the experimental setup. SSHG is ideal for monitoring voltage-induced reversible adsorption and desorption, as exemplified for core-shell gold-silver NPs ca. 16 - 20 nm in size (**Fig. 7D**).¹¹⁶ The surface specificity of SSHG arises from the vanishing of the second-order nonlinear susceptibility in centrosymmetric media within the electric dipole approximation.¹⁴⁵

4.2. Physical position and three-phase contact angle of the nanoparticles

In order to understand the measured conductive, catalytic or plasmonic activity of a gold nanofilm, the physical positions of individual AuNPs within the nanofilm need to be determined with nanometre accuracy in terms of interparticle spacing and θ_0 values. The characterisation of AuNPs on solid supports is dominated by electron and scanning probe microscopy techniques (*i.e.*, scanning/transmission electron microscopy (SEM/TEM), and scanning probe microscopy (SPM) such as atomic force microscopy (AFM) and scanning tunneling microscopy (STM)). However, the motion of AuNPs on a fluidic interface makes such *in situ* analysis at liquid-liquid interfaces exceptionally difficult. *Ex situ* analysis, for example by SEM/TEM, *via* transferring the gold nanofilms to solid supports may cause alteration of the initial microstructure, lead to the formation of drying artefacts and, finally, to incorrect interpretation of the obtained data.

Recent reviews have provided an overview of common techniques applied to determine θ_0 values of various nanomaterials at fluidic interfaces.^{146,147} Techniques such as capillary rise methods, surface-pressure isotherms or drop shape analysis measure macroscale interfacial properties related to θ_0 through theory, and therefore are indirect. The drawback of these techniques are an inability to analyse the distribution of θ_0 values. Only a single average θ_0 value can be extracted and relies on assumptions that tend to break down at the nanoscale. However, using microscopy to observe floating particles, Snoeynick *et al.*¹⁴⁸ obtained the distribution of θ_0 with good statistics for 1 μm polystyrene spheres at the interface of water-glycerol and water-decane.

One promising technique designed to overcome these issues is *freeze-fracture shadow casting (FreSCa) cryo-SEM*.^{149,150} This technique was used to image ca. 100 nm AuNPs *in situ* at water-decane interfaces and additionally determine θ_0 values. As the name suggests, the AuNP functionalised liquid-liquid interface is frozen in a liquid propane jet with a speed of up to 10⁶ K

s^{-1} , then cracked open and imaged. The key is that the interface acts as a weak fracture plane that is preferentially exposed on fracturing, see **Fig. 7E**. Techniques that trap AuNPs in gels, followed by analysis with SEM or AFM, have also been developed.¹⁵¹ However, potential drawbacks of both FreSCa cryo-SEM and gel-trapping techniques are the deformation of the interface due to the freezing/gelling process and difficulties providing statistically significant individual data points to evaluate the distribution of θ_0 values at the interface.

Costa *et al.* successfully imaged SiO_2 NP monolayers self-assembled at a water-heptane interface with an unprecedented lateral resolution of <10 nm using *amplitude-modulation AFM*,¹⁵² see **Fig. 7F** for a scheme of the experimental setup. The development of such real-space *in situ* imaging techniques will allow in-plane structural information, such as the interparticle spacing, to be gathered on a localised area of the interface. This is in sharp contrast to reciprocal techniques, such as X-ray reflectivity (discussed *vide infra*), where structural information is averaged over the finite size of the radiation beam and non-periodic isolated AuNP aggregates or defects in the nanofilm may not be easily detected.

Fig. 7. Variety of methods to locate nanoparticles at the liquid-liquid interface. (A) (i) is a schematic of a 4-electrode electrochemical cell configured for either *X-ray surface scattering measurements* or *quasi-elastic light scattering (QELS)* interfacial tension measurements (CE₁ and CE₂ are made of Pt mesh; RE₁ and RE₂ are Ag/AgCl reference electrodes). (ii) Electrocapillary curve generated using QELS; *i.e.*, a plot of interfacial tension measurements of the water-oil interface as a function of the Galvani potential difference ($\Delta\phi_0^W$) with AuNPs (blue) and without AuNPs (red). Adapted with permission from Ref. ¹⁸. Copyright 2014 American Chemical Society. (B) Calculated *specific capacitance curves* (lines) are compared to the data measured (symbols; from Ref. ⁸⁸) for various concentrations of AuNPs in the bulk aqueous electrolyte: $c_1=0.42$ nM, $c_2=0.67$ nM, $c_3=1.26$ nM. “Blank” refers to the unpopulated interface. Adapted from Ref. ¹⁴³ with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry. (C) Schematic of the electrochemical *Time-Resolved Surface Second Harmonic Generation (TR-SSHG)* experimental setup (CE = counter electrode, RE = reference electrode, Aq = aqueous phase, and Org = organic phase). Adapted with permission from Ref. ¹⁴⁴. Copyright 2014 American Chemical Society. (D) SSHG intensity (symbols) and Galvani potential difference (solid black line) as a function of time at the water-DCE interface for (triangles) Au_{0.9}Ag_{0.1} NPs and (circles) Au_{0.6}Ag_{0.4} NPs. Adapted with

permission from Ref. ¹¹⁶. Copyright 2007 American Chemical Society. (E) Schematics of the sample preparation for *freeze-fracture shadow casting (FreSCa) cryo-SEM* imaging. Reprinted by permission from Macmillan Publishers Ltd: Nature Communications, Ref. ¹⁵⁰, copyright 2011. (F) Operational scheme of *amplitude-modulation AFM* at a water-heptane interface and images of the NP monolayers. The depth of the water layer confined by a mica container is kept lower than 100 μm and the cantilever is excited by photothermal actuation (blue laser) inside the heptane drop. Adapted with permission from Ref. ¹⁵². Copyright 2016 American Chemical Society.

4.3. X-ray reflectivity and scattering

Several techniques based on scattering of X-rays from liquid-liquid interfaces are capable of determining *in situ* both in-plane and out-of-plane structural information on floating gold nanofilms.^{18,135,153,154}

X-ray reflectivity measurements identify variations in electron density perpendicular to the liquid-liquid interface,^{57,155} the experimental setup is identical to that for QELS as shown in **Fig. 7A(i)**. Schlossmann and co-workers showed that the resulting electron density profiles allow the precise interfacial location of a monolayer of 2 nm AuNPs to be determined with sub-nanometre resolution as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$.¹⁸ Under experimental conditions that induce very dense arrangements of AuNPs at the liquid-liquid interface, for example upon lateral compression,¹⁵³ X-ray reflectivity measurements provide evidence for the formation of interfacial bi- or tri-layers of AuNPs.

Grazing-incidence small angle x-ray scattering (GISAXS) reveals the 2D ordering of the AuNPs within the gold nanofilm, for example changes in the lattice spacing or interparticle separation distance as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$ ¹⁸ or solution ionic strength¹³⁵ have been demonstrated. Typically, X-ray scattering experiments have been combined with other techniques to gain deeper insights. Schlossmann and co-workers¹⁸ combined insights from X-ray reflectivity, GISAXS, electrocapillary curves and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations (all as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$) to demonstrate that hydrophobic TB^- anions in the organic phase condense onto the surface of very positively charged AuNPs coated with trimethylammonium terminated ligands at the aqueous-organic interface. Snapshots of the MD simulations at various time periods are shown in **Fig. 8**. This is strong experimental proof of the concept of TB^- acting as a “promoter”, as described by Bell and co-workers for the case of tetrabutylammonium (TBA^+) cations condensing onto the surface of very negatively charged AuNPs.^{2,82} Schlossmann and co-workers¹⁸ show that the small 2 nm AuNPs are drawn across the interface into the low polarity organic phase by shielding their

charge with hydrophobic counter-ions. Meanwhile, Vellemann *et al.*¹³⁵ utilised X-ray reflectivity, grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) and optical reflectance (discussed *vide infra*) as complementary techniques to independently verify the decrease in interparticle spacing and increase in AuNP surface coverage with increasing ionic strength in either the aqueous or organic phase.

Fig. 8. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation of nanoparticles at liquid-liquid interfaces. Time sequence snapshots of the submersion of a AuNP from an aqueous (top) to an organic (bottom) electrolyte phase accompanied by the exchange of loosely bound Cl^- ions (blue) in the aqueous phase for condensed organic TB^+ ions (red) in the organic phase. Adapted with permission from Ref. ¹⁸. Copyright 2014 American Chemical Society.

4.4. Optical reflectivity and scattering

Optical reflectivity measurements have been used to investigate propagating SPR due to strong plasmon coupling in densely packed interfacial gold nanofilms.^{89,91,156} Using a pseudo-Kretschmann configuration, Cohanoschi *et al.* highlighted that a 10^3 times enhancement of the interfacial fluorescence of dyes is possible at water-xylene interfaces at the surface plasmon resonance angle (θ_{SPR}) in the presence of interfacial gold nanofilms. The enhancement was attributed to the electric field enhancement in the plasmonic “hot-spots” and the reduction of the

fluorescence lifetime of dye molecules in close vicinity to the metal surface.¹⁵⁶ θ_{SPR} is the angle of the incident light hitting the interfacial gold nanofilm that leads to a minimum (or dip) in reflectance at a specific wavelength. Also using a pseudo-Kretschmann configuration (see **Fig. 9A(i)**), Hojeij *et al.* produced clear experimental evidence of the dip in reflectance beyond the critical angle due to SPR absorption by the interfacial gold nanofilm, closely matching theoretical calculations,⁸⁹ see **Fig. 9A(ii) and (iii)**.

SPR is also sensitive to changes in refractive index of the medium (discussed in detail in Section 5.2 *vide infra*), measured as the change in reflected light passing through a prism and reflected off of the back of the interfacial gold nanofilm. The “back” of the interfacial gold nanofilm can refer to the oil-side or water-side depending on the density of the chosen oil phase. Thus, a low density oil phase such as toluene will be on top of the water phase and, when illuminated from the bottom, water is at the “back” of the interfacial gold nanofilm, and *vice versa* for a high density oil phase such as TFT. Therefore, SPR-based nanoplasmonic sensors based on interfacial gold nanofilms using a pseudo-Kretschmann configuration are envisioned.

Girault and co-workers developed a setup with robotic arms to change the angle of incident light hitting the interfacial gold nanofilms, shown in **Fig. 9B**. The latter setup has been used to generate optical reflectivity data allowing the quantification of the influence of a host of variables (AuNP size, interfacial surface coverage and light wavelength, polarisation and angle of incidence, presence of surfactant, applied $\Delta_0^w \phi$) on the effectiveness of variously prepared interfacial gold nanofilms to act as nanoplasmonic mirrors.^{17,90}

Smirnov *et al.*⁷ probed the optical extinction and reflectance of interfacial gold nanofilms that encapsulate the entirety of an oil droplet using an *integration sphere* (**Fig. 9C**). Additionally, they imaged gold nanofilms *in situ* with μm resolution with *optical microscopy* revealing the formation of micro-scale cracks and wrinkles. Comparison of SEM and TEM images obtained with transfer of the nanofilm on a solid substrate show similar features, confirming that the structure of the film can stay more or less intact during the transfer.⁷

Furthermore, Vellemann *et al.*¹³⁵ used a commercial reflectivity probe positioned at 90° to the liquid-liquid interface (see **Fig. 9D**) to monitor the red-shift in SPR reflectance maxima as a result of enhanced plasmonic coupling between AuNPs due to decreasing interparticle spacing with

increasing ionic strength in either the aqueous or organic phase (allowing calibration of a so-called “plasmonic ruler”).

As detailed in Section 3.4, decreasing the interparticle gap in a gold nanofilm causes a near-exponential increase in the sensitivity of the responses of SPR and SERS-based nanoplasmonic sensors, as well as an exponential increase in the conductivity of the gold nanofilm. Thus, the creation of calibrated plasmonic rulers using easily accessible optical spectroscopic techniques, as described by Vellemann *et al.*¹³⁵, provides a precise guide to tune the interparticle gaps through addition of salt, applying an electric field, *etc.* in real time. The latter will be hugely beneficial to tune the strength of homogeneous plasmonic hotspots, necessary to optimise the responses of nanoplasmonic sensors using floating gold nanofilms, and also as a guide to predicting the conductivity of floating gold nanofilms. Most recently, Velleman *et al.*¹⁵⁷ further demonstrated the reduction of interparticle distance between AuNPs in the nanofilm *in situ* at a water-DCE interface as a function of pH, which led to a 20- to 40-fold increase of Raman intensity. Moreover, these changes were monitored in real time.¹⁵⁷

Fig. 9. Reflectance measurements from a liquid-liquid interface functionalised with a nanofilm. (A)(i) Schematic of the experimental setup to measure surface plasmon resonance (SPR) at a gold nanofilm floating at a liquid-liquid interface using a pseudo-Kretschmann configuration. (A)(ii) Calculated and (A)(iii) experimental SPR curves for a gold nanofilm floating at a water-DCE interface for an excitation wavelength of 544 nm (full line: 16 nm Au film, dotted line: 13 nm Au film). Adapted from Ref. ⁸⁹ with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry. (B) Image of an experimental setup with robotic arms to investigate the angular dependence of the laser reflectance from interfacial gold nanofilms. The setup consists of robotic arms, a laser light source, various optical components and a detector, all of which move simultaneously as the angle of the laser incident to the gold nanofilms is varied. Adapted from Ref. ¹⁷ with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry. (C) Reflectance and extinction spectra acquisition for interfacial gold nanofilms *in situ* by UV-Vis-NIR with a white integrating sphere. "Sample" (with the gold nanofilm coating the organic droplet) reflectance spectra were obtained at a single gold nanofilm interface on one side of the quartz cell. "Sample" extinction spectra were measured through two gold nanofilms at opposite walls of the quartz cuvette. Q, w, org, and NF, are acronyms for quartz, water, organic solvent and gold nanofilm. Adapted from Ref. ⁷ with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry. (D) Schematic describing the self-assembly of AuNPs at a water-DCE

interface when either NaCl or TBATPB was added to the aqueous or organic phase, respectively. The assembled floating gold nanofilm was analysed by X-ray reflectivity and diffraction to obtain structural information, and with optical reflectance to study the plasmon coupling between the AuNPs. Adapted from Ref. ¹³⁵ with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

4.5. Electrochemical techniques

Scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) at liquid-liquid interfaces can be used to probe the local conductivity or potentially characterise redox electrocatalysis reactions taking place at an interfacial gold nanofilm. The working principle of SECM involves the continuous recycling of a redox mediator, either in the aqueous or organic phase, between the tip of a biased micro- or nano-electrode and the surface of the interfacial gold nanofilm, see **Fig. 10A**. If a microelectrode (biased positively to oxidise the mediator) approaches an area of the interface that is non-conductive, a gradual decrease of the measured current is observed due to confinement of the semi-spherical diffusion field at the surface between the microelectrode and the liquid-liquid interface (**Fig. 10A(i)**). The latter causes a depletion of the reduced species and accumulation of oxidised species, and is called “negative feedback”. A non-conductive interface can simply mean the absence of AuNPs at that local area on the interface, or the presence of AuNPs with such a large interparticle spacing that charge transport cannot propagate across the interfacial gold nanofilm. The latter was shown by Fang *et al.* where negative feedback was observed until a sufficiently large AuNP surface coverage (and therefore small interparticle distance) was reached to allow charge transport across at least μm^2 -sized portions of the interfacial gold nanofilm,⁹⁰ see **Fig. 10B**. For these conductive densely packed interfacial arrays of AuNPs, the measured current increases on approaching the interface as the oxidised species are reduced by the AuNPs (**Fig. 10(A)(ii)**). The latter is called “positive feedback” and the conductive gold nanofilm is recharged by electron injection from another redox species in the opposite phase at any point on the gold nanofilm (*i.e.*, at a considerable distance from where the microelectrode is positioned). Although as yet not demonstrated for redox electrocatalysis with gold nanofilms, in a related study, SECM has been used to monitor photo-induced water oxidation at ITIES functionalised with nanosized bismuth vanadate (BiVO_4) crystals.¹⁵⁸

Ion transfer voltammetry can be also used to roughly estimate the surface coverage of the nanofilms. NPs adsorbed at the interface reduce the available surface area for IT, effectively

blocking the surface.²⁰ As discussed by Amatore *et al.*,¹⁵⁹ a blocking layer at the electrode surface leads to a decreased apparent standard rate constant for the electron transfer reaction ($k_{\text{app}}^0 = k^0(1 - \theta)$, where θ is the surface coverage of the blocking porous layer). The same approach is true for the nanofilm covering the ITIES, see **Fig. 10C**. Hence, a simple estimation of the apparent standard ion transfer constant for the transferring ion by the method of Nicholson allows estimation of the surface coverage if the rate constant on the clean surface is known,²⁰ see **Fig. 10D**. Other techniques successfully used to characterise the coverage of porous layers on solid electrodes, like chronoamperometry,¹⁶⁰ could be also utilised at liquid-liquid interfaces for IT reactions.

Fig. 10. Electrochemical methods used to characterise nanofilms at liquid-liquid interfaces. Schemes of *scanning electrochemical microscopy* (SECM) experiments with (A) (i) negative feedback at a bare water-oil interface and (ii) positive feedback at a floating gold nanofilm at a water-oil interface. (B) SECM approach curves with a Pt microelectrode (radius, $a = 10 \mu\text{m}$; $\text{RG} = 7$) to a water-[heptane/DCE] interface in the presence of different AuNP surface coverages. The oil phase contained 2 mM DMFc and 2 mM BATB. The translation rate was $1 \mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Adapted with permission from Ref. ⁹⁰. Copyright 2013 American Chemical Society. (C) Schematic representation of the cross-sectional view of the ITIES partially occupied by a gold nanofilm. The lines show the diffusion profiles of ion concentration. Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁰. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. (D) Ion transfer CVs (IR compensated) of 25 μM tetramethylammonium cations (TMA^+) in the aqueous phase at a water-TFT interface (i) without a gold nanofilm and (ii) with a gold nanofilm composed of 12 nm AUNPs. The apparent standard ion transfer constant (k_{app}^0) for TMA^+ was calculated by the method of Nicholson, allowing

estimation of the interfacial AuNP surface coverage (θ). Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁰. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society.

4.6. Summary

A summary of the main experimental techniques used to probe AuNP adsorption at liquid-liquid interfaces, and the resulting properties of gold nanofilms formed at liquid-liquid interfaces, is provided in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Summary of experimental techniques applied to the characterisation of AuNP adsorption at liquid-liquid interfaces and the properties of the resulting floating gold nanofilms.

Experimental technique	Information / Measurement Results	Ref.
Quasi-elastic light scattering (QELS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring the adsorption of AuNPs to the ITIES as a function of applied $\Delta_0^w \phi$ (electrocapillary curve). 	18,115
Pendant drop tensiometry		136–140,142
Electrochemical capacitance		88,115,143
Surface Second Harmonic Generation (SSHG)		116,145
Freeze-fracture shadow casting (FreSCa) cryo-SEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>In situ</i> determination of θ_0 for AuNPs adsorbed at a liquid-liquid interface. 	149,150
Gel-trapping techniques followed by SEM or AFM		151
Amplitude modulation atomic force microscopy (AFM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>In situ</i> <u>real-space</u> determination of interparticle separation for AuNPs adsorbed at a liquid-liquid interface. 	152
X-ray reflectivity		18,153

Grazing-incidence small angle x-ray scattering (GISAXS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In-plane <i>in situ</i> <u>reciprocal-space</u> determination of interparticle separation for AuNPs adsorbed at a liquid-liquid interface. 	18
Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Precise determination of AuNP out-of-plane shifts as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$. 	135
Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulation of AuNP adsorption at a liquid-liquid interface, <i>e.g.</i>, probing the influence of organic electrolyte counter-ion condensation on the surface of a AuNP during adsorption. 	18
Reflection measurements in Pseudo-Kretschmann configuration (prism) or with robotic arms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Angular dependence of reflectivity from floating gold nanofilms at a liquid-liquid interface at a given wavelength. Determination of θ_{SPR}. 	17,89–91,156
UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy with an integration sphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflectivity and extinction spectra <i>vs.</i> coverage of the interface 	7
Commercial reflectivity fiber probe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring red and blue-shifts of SPR and SPC extinction bands to determine <i>in situ</i> the interparticle separation for AuNPs adsorbed at a liquid-liquid interface. 	135
Scanning Electrochemical Microscopy (SECM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conductivity measurements of floating gold nanofilms at the ITIES. Probing catalytic properties of NPs adsorbed at the liquid-liquid interface. 	90,158
Ion transfer (IT) voltammetry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ion permeability Estimation of the surface coverage of AuNPs at the ITIES. 	20

For solid-liquid interfaces, electrochemical capacitance measurements are useful to probe the nanofilm porosity.¹⁶¹ SSHG is well known from metal island films,¹⁶² and has been utilised for designing a nonlinear plasmonic nanoruler with high sensitivity.¹⁶³ Surface probe techniques are much easier to employ for films assembled at solid-liquid interfaces, with techniques like SEM, TEM, STM and AMF used routinely. Additionally, spectroscopic techniques have been widely utilised to characterise optical properties of superlattices. More specialised techniques such as liquid cell transmission electron microscopy (LC-TEM) have been utilised to follow NP self-assembly *in situ*.¹⁶⁴ Both grazing-incidence (GISAXS) and small angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) have been widely used for investigation of NP superlattices. They also allow statistical determination of superlattice grain size and size distributions over larger areas than accessible with electron microscopy due to systematic mapping of the sample.¹⁶⁵ SAXS measurements were also used for spatial mapping of the grain size, orientation, uniformity, strain, or crystal projections and polymorphs.¹⁶⁵ SAXS measurements of NPs have been recently reviewed.¹⁶⁶ For example, GISAXS was utilised to follow swelling of the film in the presence of volatile organic compounds.¹⁶⁷

5. APPLICATIONS OF FLOATING GOLD NANOFILMS

5.1 Redox electrocatalysis

As described in a recent review, electrocatalysis is catalysis of electron transfer at the electrode surface (catalysed by the electrode material itself or by a catalyst attached to the electrode surface), while redox electrocatalysis is catalysis of electron transfer between two redox couples, catalysed by a floating conductive catalyst.¹²⁵ Electrocatalysis and redox electrocatalysis are topics of pivotal importance impacting a huge variety of fields ranging from corrosion science, fuel cell and battery research, electro-organic synthesis, electroanalytical sensor development to waste-water purification.^{125,168} To optimise the performance of NPs towards electrocatalysis, a burgeoning area of research concerns support-induced effects.^{169,170} For example, the supporting material for AuNPs can deeply affect their activities, as exhibited for AuNPs supported on carbon and on titania in the CO oxidation reaction.¹⁷¹

Electrochemistry of catalytic interfacial gold nanofilms at the ITIES has several distinguishing features in comparison to electrochemical studies of AuNPs on solid electrode surfaces. Most

strikingly, the electrocatalytic activity of interfacial adsorbed AuNPs can be studied in a “contactless” manner, free from the influence of an underlying support. Just as with solid electrodes, the ITIES allows direct measurement of the electrocatalytic impact of gold nanofilms by measurement of charge transfer across the interface corresponding to electron transfer events. At solid electrode interfaces the rate of an electrocatalysed reaction is controlled by varying the electrode potential and concentrations of oxidised to reduced species initially present in solution. The degree of freedom of this system is one, as the system is fully characterised by the mass balance equation ($\text{Ox} + e^- \Leftrightarrow \text{Red}$) and the Nernst equation:

$$E = E^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{a_{\text{Ox}}}{a_{\text{Red}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where E is the electrode potential, E^0 is the standard redox potential of Ox/Red, a is activity (where the activity is related to the concentration, c , by $a = \gamma c$, taking into account the activity coefficient, γ , that becomes 1 for infinite dilution) and R , T and F are the gas constant, temperature and Faraday’s constant, respectively. Attractively, the ITIES has in fact two degrees of freedom, as five variables are interconnected by two mass balance equations and the Nernst equation.¹⁷² The first mass balance equation concerns Ox/Red species in the aqueous phase and the second concerns Ox/Red species in the organic phase, resulting in $\text{Ox}_1^w + \text{Red}_2^o \Leftrightarrow \text{Red}_1^w + \text{Ox}_2^o$, where superscripts w and o refer to aqueous and organic phases, respectively. Thus, the Nernst equation for IET across the ITIES is:¹⁷²

$$\Delta_o^w \phi = \Delta_o^w \phi_{\text{ET}}^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{a_{\text{Red}_1}^w a_{\text{Ox}_2}^o}{a_{\text{Ox}_1}^w a_{\text{Red}_2}^o} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta_o^w \phi_{\text{ET}}^0$ is the standard redox potential for the IET reaction: $\Delta_o^w \phi_{\text{ET}}^0 = [E_{\text{Ox}_2/\text{Red}_2}^0]_{\text{SHE}}^o - [E_{\text{Ox}_1/\text{Red}_1}^0]_{\text{SHE}}^w$, superscript 0 refers to the standard value and SHE refers to standard hydrogen electrode scale.

This IET reaction can take place also without catalysts, but a gold nanofilm deposited at the interface may be utilised to significantly enhance the reaction rate. Effectively, the AuNPs act as conductive bipolar electrodes facilitating catalysis *via* direct IET (through Fermi level equilibration)^{20,173} between a lipophilic electron donor and a hydrophilic electron acceptor, or *vice*

versa (see Fig. 11). Finite element method simulations have also been used to study this process.^{174,175}

Fig. 11. Mechanism of interfacial redox electrocatalysis by floating gold nanofilms. Equilibration of the Fermi level of the electrons in a single AuNP within a gold nanofilm (E_F^{NP}) adsorbed at a liquid-liquid interface with those of two redox couples in solution, a hydrophilic electron acceptor species (A) in the aqueous phase and a hydrophobic electron donor species (D) in the organic phase. The AuNP is charged during this process by D , for example ferrocene (Fc). The AuNP acts as an “interfacial reservoir of electrons”, and the final position of E_F^{NP} (a turquoise line for $\Delta\phi^w = 0$ V and a red line for $\Delta\phi^w = 0.3$ V, respectively) is determined by the kinetics of both the oxidation half-reaction on the organic side of the interfacial gold nanofilm and the reduction half-reaction on the aqueous side (for example O₂ reduction). IET between the two redox couples *via* the conductive AuNP, and the provision of a catalytic surface in the specific case of O₂ reduction, significantly enhance the kinetics of IET. The standard redox potentials of all redox couples are expressed *versus* both the Standard Hydrogen Electrode (SHE) and Absolute Vacuum Scale (AVS), respectively, and the organic phase is TFT. Adapted from Ref. ¹⁹ with permission from Elsevier, copyright 2016.

Moreover, the AuNPs provide a catalytic surface to further negate the kinetic barriers to IET at bare liquid-liquid interfaces. Additional thermodynamic driving force can then be provided by adjusting $\Delta\phi^w$ to establish further control over both the rate of a reaction and the direction of electron transfer across the interface. As a proof-of-concept, interfacial gold nanofilms were shown to effectively catalyse IET between a lipophilic electron donor redox couple, ferrocenium

cation/ferrocene, and a hydrophilic electron acceptor redox couple, ferri/ferro-cyanide,²⁰ see **Fig. 12A**. The peak-to-peak separation for IET reduced significantly from above 90 mV in the absence of the gold nanofilm (**Fig. 12B**) to between 65 and 70 mV in its presence (**Fig. 12C**). Additionally, a clear shift of the ratio of the forward and reverse peak current towards unity was observed in the presence of the gold nanofilm. Furthermore, dissolved oxygen (O₂) in the aqueous phase was reduced to H₂O₂ and H₂O by IET from either the lipophilic electron donor redox couple decamethylferrocenium cation/decamethylferrocene,¹⁹ as shown in **Fig. 12D-E**, or 1,1'-dimethylferrocenium cation/1,1'-decamethylferrocene.²¹ Recently, redox electrocatalysis of O₂ reduction was also utilised to study Pt NP impacts upon a microscopic liquid-liquid interface, extending the NP impact studies to collisions at liquid-liquid interfaces.¹⁷⁶

Beyond gold nanofilms, redox electrocatalysis of energy related reactions such as the biphasic O₂ reduction reaction (ORR)^{38,177–205} and biphasic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER)^{185,201,206–217} has also been demonstrated numerous times by immobilisation of catalytic NPs ranging from inorganic nanomaterials (*e.g.*, Pt,¹⁸⁵ MoS₂,²⁰⁸ Mo₂C,²¹⁰ Cu₂CoSnS₄,²¹³ *etc.*) to carbon-supported nanocomposites (*e.g.*, Cu NPs on carbon nanotubes)²¹⁵ at the ITIES. Furthermore, redox photoelectrocatalysis of the water oxidation reaction (WOR) has been achieved by immobilisation of BiVO₄ semiconductor NPs at the ITIES.¹⁵⁸ These burgeoning areas of redox (photo)electrocatalysis of energy related reactions by ITIES functionalised with nanomaterials (beyond gold nanofilms) are very exciting current avenues of research and as such have been the subject of two recent comprehensive reviews by Peljo *et al.*¹²⁵ and Poltorak *et al.*⁷¹

NP superlattices formed at solid-liquid interfaces can be utilised for electrocatalysis as well as for heterogeneous catalysis, as reviewed by Boles *et al.*³³ and by Henry.²¹⁸ For example, Au nanocrystals were found to be highly active for oxidation of CO when assembled on metal oxide surfaces,²¹⁹ most likely due to the contact electrification.^{220–222} Binary superlattices employing Au-Fe₃O₄ and Pt-CeO₂ and pairs have been employed for CO oxidation²²³ and methanol decomposition,²²⁴ respectively. Curiously, electrocatalysis utilising superlattices has not been explored in detail. Instead, significant attention has been focused on NPs supported on carbon, and on single NP electrochemistry.²²⁵ However, recent examples demonstrated binary Pd-Pt superlattices for electrocatalytic O₂ reduction,²²⁶ and AuNP superlattices for electrochemical detection of microRNA-21 utilising toluidine blue as a hybridisation indicator.²²⁷ Additionally, polyelectrolyte/AuNP hybrid films have been utilised for NO sensing,²²⁸ and similar layer-by-layer

films of IrO₂ particles for O₂ evolution.^{229,230} On the other hand, NP arrays have been utilised for multivariable gas and vapor sensing using a panoply of techniques ranging from impedance spectroscopy to optical methods measuring the reflected light.²³¹

HET= Heterogeneous ET

ET = Electron Transfer

IT = Ion Transfer

EC = Electrocatalysis

Fig. 12. Experimental evidence of interfacial redox electrocatalysis by floating gold nanofilms. (A) Possible mechanisms, each leading to a measurable current across the ITIES when an electron donor species (D , such as the ferrocenium cation/ferrocene redox couple; Fc^+/Fc) is present in the organic phase and an electron acceptor species (A , such as ferri/ferrocyanide; $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$) is present in the aqueous phase: (i) bimolecular IET, (ii) a homogeneous electron transfer-ion transfer (ET-IT) mechanism, and (iii) interfacial redox electrocatalysis with the floating gold nanofilm acting as a bipolar electrode. The orange arrow indicates the ET reaction with a rate constant, k^0 . Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁰. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. CVs of ET between the oil solubilised Fc^+/Fc redox couple and the aqueous $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ redox couple, with various ratios between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} investigated, both (B) in the absence and (C) in the presence of an interfacial gold nanofilm. Scan rate for all CVs was 10 mV s^{-1} and the organic phase was TFT. Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁰. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. (D) Mechanism of O_2 reduction in the aqueous phase by charging a floating gold nanofilm with an electron donor (such as decamethylferrocene, DMFc) in the organic phase. The gold nanofilm acts as a barrier-free shortcut for IET to the aqueous phase. Adapted from Ref. ¹⁹ with permission from Elsevier, copyright 2016. (E) CVs provide clear evidence of IET between DMFc and aqueous O_2 via the floating gold nanofilm due to the appearance of a significant current wave at $\Delta_o^w \phi = 50 \text{ mV}$ under aerobic conditions only. The scan rate was 25 mV s^{-1} in all cases and the organic phase was TFT. Adapted from Ref. ¹⁹ with permission from Elsevier, copyright 2016.

5.2 Nanoplasmonics

Localised surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) occurs when the incident light frequency impacting a AuNP is resonant with the collective oscillation of the conduction band electrons.¹²⁶ LSPR leads to a marked enhancement in the local (near field) electromagnetic field at the surface of the AuNP in comparison to the incident light. Yang *et al.* have used a three dimensional finite difference time domain (3D-FDTD) method to clarify the LSPR-based optical properties of AuNPs adsorbed at the water–oil interface, including near field distribution and far field absorption.²³² In the case of a AuNP adsorbed at a liquid-liquid interface, the presence of an underlying substrate (*i.e.*, the oil phase) distorts the distribution of the plasmon field around the AuNP (see **Fig. 13(i)-(iv)**). The latter is due to the change of the dielectric function at one side of the AuNP causing the LSPR to be either red- or blue-shifted.^{7,232–237}

It is important to distinguish that “localised” in LSPR refers to the plasmonic response of separate, non-interacting AuNPs only. This is typically the case for AuNPs dispersed in a colloidal solution or for a hypothetical situation where a single AuNP adsorbs at a liquid-liquid interface, as modelled by Yang *et al.* in **Fig. 13(i)-(iv)**.²³² However, each AuNP in a gold nanofilm inevitably interacts with its neighbouring AuNPs, and thereby all AuNPs in a gold nanofilm affect each other’s

plasmonic responses. Thus, the optical response of a film of NPs contains two plasmon peaks. The first one refers to extinction peaks of out-of-plane (transverse) AuNP plasmon oscillations for interacting AuNPs adsorbed at a water-oil interface, known simply as surface plasmon resonance (SPR) bands. The second one corresponds to in-plane (longitudinal) propagating plasmon oscillations that give rise to the appearance of additional “coupling mode” extinction peaks and is called the surface plasmon coupling (SPC) band. Usually the SPC band is red-shifted in comparison to the SPR band. **Fig. 13B** demonstrates the presence of both SPR and SPC bands in calculated absorbance spectrum for a dimer of interacting AuNPs at water-DCE interface. Further, a series of works carried out by the group of Prof. Kornyshev revealed a high correlation between theoretically predicted¹³³ and experimentally obtained¹³⁵ absorbance and reflectance spectra for nanofilms at liquid-liquid interfaces. A significant number of articles focus on the plasmonics of NP superlattices at solid-liquid interfaces,²³⁸ as highlighted in recent reviews.^{31,33–35,76,239–241} The basic physics and applications are similar to those at liquid-liquid interfaces, however, nanoplasmonics at solid-liquid interfaces is a field of its own, and covered in detail for example by Gwo *et al.*³⁴

The “hot-spots” formed between plasmonically coupled AuNPs experience hugely enhanced electromagnetic fields. Indeed, Yang *et al.*'s study concluded that in “hot-spots” between adjacent AuNPs in an interfacial gold nanofilm the efficiency of Raman scattering was enhanced in excess of 10^7 – 10^9 fold upon excitation with a laser of appropriate wavelength.²³² Such a phenomenon is known as surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS),²⁴² an analytical method capable of providing molecular fingerprint information with ultrahigh surface sensitivity.

Fig. 13. Distortion of the distribution of the plasmon fields around AuNPs floating at a liquid-liquid interface. (A) Finite difference time domain (FDTD) calculated SERS electromagnetic enhancement distribution in the yz-plane at the frequency of LSPR for various interfacial positions of a AuNP: (i) 2 nm above the interface, (ii) 2 nm submerged into the oil, (iii) 2 nm remaining in water, and (iv) 2 nm below the interface. The dashed line represents the water-oil interface. (B) Calculated absorption spectra of AuNP dimers (red line) at the water–DCE interface and the corresponding electric field distribution for three peaks (SPR “water mode”, SPR “oil mode” and SPC “coupling mode”). Adapted from Ref. ²³² with permission from the PCCP Owner Societies.

The SPR and SPC extinction bands observed for AuNPs represent both light absorption and scattering by the AuNPs. Reflection can be considered a special case for light scattered along the specular direction. Furthermore, the AuNPs characteristic SPR wavelengths shift with changes of the medium refractive-index. Thus, as the introduction of analyte molecules influences the bulk refractive index of the AuNPs environment, the resulting shifts in SPR maxima position are the basis of SPR sensors.²⁴³ Both extinction (*i.e.*, transmission expressed in -log units) and reflectance measurements have been used to monitor shifts in the SPR maxima position on introduction of an

analyte, with Kedem *et al.* demonstrating that reflectance measurements are more sensitive due to the dominance of absorption in transmission spectroscopy.²⁴⁴

Thus, using interfacial gold nanofilm sensors, the resulting SERS- or SPR-based nanoplasmonic sensors have the potential to facilitate the identification of single molecules attached, or located in close proximity, to the AuNP surface. The defect-free nature of the interface allows the creation of gold nanofilms with an exceptionally homogeneous distribution of “hot-spots”, difficult to achieve using either bottom-up or top-down approaches on solid substrates. This key feature maximises the reproducibility of the resulting SERS- or SPR-based nanoplasmonic sensors. Prospective floating gold nanofilm based SERS and SPR sensors will be discussed in more in detail in Section 6.1. However, superlattice formation of SERS active NPs at solid substrates has already been demonstrated, and SERS is actually one of the main applications of AuNP nanofilms at solid-liquid interfaces.^{34,113,245} Additionally, three-phase self-assembly, utilising both solid-liquid and liquid-liquid interfaces, can also be performed for preparation of SERS substrates of high Raman enhancement factors.¹¹³

5.3 Optical applications

A series of theoretical studies^{129–134} have shown that coupling between localised surface plasmons of AuNPs in an interfacial gold nanofilm leads to significant reflection of light from the interface. The latter is perhaps surprising as only a monolayer of AuNPs is required to achieve this nanoplasmonic mirror-effect. When incident light strikes strongly coupled interfacial AuNPs, light is scattered with phase coherence from AuNP to AuNP (in contrast to plasmonically non-coupled single AuNPs that scatter light in random directions according to Mie theory). This results in a very high reflection coefficient for an interfacial gold nanofilm, with reflection dominating over transmission; and dependent on the wavelength of incident light.

From a practical point-of-view, Smirnov *et al.*⁷ have shown that the size of the AuNPs is critical. Small AuNPs (less than 15 nm in diameter) are capable of effectively absorbing incident light, whereas larger AuNPs (above 25-30 nm) are more suited for liquid mirrors applications due to efficient reflection of light (in agreement with theory).⁷ The larger AuNPs absorb very little light due to being low dissipation materials that facilitate long-lived plasmons.¹³⁰ By comparison, NPs of aluminum, for example, would absorb significant amounts of light at the interface *via*

dissipation of surface plasmons.¹³⁰ Thus, the reversible electrovariable movement of AuNPs both to and from the interface (“on and off” mirrors) and in-plane of the interface (shutters) as a function of $\Delta_0^w \phi$ lays the foundations for a host of potential technological applications of interfacial gold nanofilms in the realm of optics.

5.4 Plasmonic photocatalysis

The topic of plasmon-enhanced photo-reactions with floating gold nanofilms is not explored in detail in this perspective. However, it is worth mentioning briefly as conflicting reports have emerged regarding whether photocurrents at porphyrin-sensitised liquid-liquid interfaces can be significantly enhanced by devising protocols that incorporate plasmonic metallic NPs into the photoactive interfacial films.^{17,91,246} Insights from such studies may potentially find applications in future artificial photosynthesis systems.^{247,248} The underlying fundamental reasons for any enhanced photocurrents are as yet unresolved with electrocatalytic and/or plasmonic factors needing to be considered. Nagatani *et al.*²⁴⁶ and Schaming *et al.*⁹¹ observed increased photocurrents that may be attributed to increased absorption due to surface plasmons and light-trapping effects, improved charge separation due to a localised intense electromagnetic field, or perhaps electron storage effects that alter the Fermi level of the interfacial gold nanofilm. Alternatively, the photocurrents may actually decrease, as observed by Gschwend *et al.*,¹⁷ as the surface area of the liquid-liquid interface becomes “blocked” with AuNPs, reducing the interfacial concentration of excited porphyrin molecules. Thus, some key questions remain unresolved. Which of the noted possible factors dominate the enhanced photo-responses seen by Nagatani *et al.* and Schaming *et al.*? Do the observations of Gschwend *et al.* negate all of the possible beneficial electrocatalytic or plasmonic attributes of the interfacial AuNPs? Each of the three studies to date introduced AuNPs to the electrochemical cell using very different experimental protocols, and therein likely lays the discrepancies between these preliminary studies.

6. PERSPECTIVE APPLICATIONS OF FLOATING GOLD NANOFILMS AT THE ITIES

6.1. Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy

A series of SERS active solid electrode substrates, *e.g.*, electrically contacted lithographic nanohole and nanopore arrays,^{249,250} periodic particle arrays prepared by nanosphere lithography

on transparent conductive oxides,^{251,252} or colloidal silver nanoparticle (AgNP) and AuNP aggregates on conductive electrodes,^{253,254} are suitable for electrochemical SERS (EC-SERS) applications. EC-SERS involves immersing these suitable SERS substrates in electrolyte solution and establishing an electrochemical double-layer at the substrate/electrolyte interface, the potential drop across which can be controlled externally by a potentiostat.^{255–257} The ultimate goal of EC-SERS is to monitor structural changes of molecules *in situ* as they are subjected to an electric field and in some cases undergo redox processes. The insights from such experiments have tremendous potential, for example we may improve our understanding of how a molecules redox activity is influenced by its immobilisation chemistry.^{258,259} The precipitous improvement in Raman instrumentation has now reached a point that the time resolution for spectra acquisition is comparable or even shorter than the charging time of the double layer capacitance for both reversible and irreversible electrochemical processes.²⁶⁰ The significance of this milestone cannot be understated as it means structural molecular information of transient intermediate species in electrochemical reactions can be directly probed *in situ*, for example during proton-coupled electron transfer reactions. The structural information gained from EC-SERS measurements can give insights that indicate potential induced (i) adsorption or desorption of molecules, (ii) molecular reorientation of molecules, (iii) rearrangement of the electrochemical double layer, or (iv) electrochemical reduction or oxidation.²⁵⁵

To date, strategies to achieve EC-SERS at interfacial gold nanofilm functionalised ITIES are rare. Virtually all SERS studies involving liquid-liquid interfaces only take advantage of their inherent ability to facilitate defect-free self-assembly of floating gold nanofilms (with uniform distribution of plasmonic hot-spots), and not the ability to controllably apply a potential difference across the ITIES. For example, nanoplasmonic SERS sensors to detect epinephrine in serum, Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , rhodamine 6G, malachite green, *p*-aminothiophenol and *p*-nitrothiophenol have been developed by either transferring floating gold nanofilms to silicon wafer, glass, paper or PDMS substrates (for example see **Fig. 14A**),^{261–270} or by their *in situ* analysis at non-polarised water-oil interfaces (for example see **Fig. 14B**).^{2,271–275} The use of flexible PDMS substrates^{261,262} is a particularly interesting strategy to vary the interparticle spacing using an external mechanical strain applied in a reversible manner (**Fig. 14C**), thereby modulating the gold nanofilms plasmonic responses (*e.g.*, towards applications in stretchable optical color filters).

The biphasic nature of SERS sensors created using floating gold nanofilms circumvents any issues regarding solubility limitations of the analyte. Both hydrophilic and hydrophobic analyte may easily come in contact with, and become pre-concentrated by attaching to, interfacial AuNPs during emulsification by sonication. Thus, simultaneous multiphase analyte detection is possible.²⁷² Additionally, tailored detection strategies can be developed to facilitate large SERS enhancements involving oil-based hydrophobic ligands binding hydrophilic target aqueous analytes (such as heavy metal ions) at the liquid-liquid interface during emulsification.²⁷⁴ Ideally, as shown in **Fig. 14D**, interfacial metal-ligand binding and attachment of the metal-ligand complexes to the interfacial AuNPs occurs simultaneously.

Fig. 14. Current state-of-the-art surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) studies utilizing liquid-liquid interfaces. (A) Schematic representation of the detection process for epinephrine (EP) by a 2D surface-enhanced resonance Raman spectroscopy (SERRS) platform. The *sample* contains EP in serum (so an aqueous solution), to which AuNPs modified with α,β -nitriloacetic acid and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ are added. The modified AuNPs *capture* the EP and *self-assemble* (due to addition of ethanol) at the water-cyclohexane interface. The self-assembled gold nanofilms, enriched with the target EP analyte, are *transferred* to a silicon substrate for *ex situ* SERRS analysis. Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁶⁴. Copyright 2017 American Chemical Society. (B) A gold nanofilm was formed at the water-toluene interface by addition of 1-dodecanethiol (DDT) and TMA⁺ ions to the biphasic cell. *In situ* SERS analysis at the liquid-liquid interface demonstrated that the interfacial morphology of the gold nanofilm was closely linked to its chemical environment (*e.g.*, in the presence of TMA⁺ alone, with varying amounts of DDT present, *etc.*). Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁷⁵. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. (C) Reflection spectra of AuNP mats under increasing strain. The AuNP mats were prepared by transferring a floating gold nanofilm formed at a water-hexane interface to a flexible PDMS

substrate. (Left panel) Uniaxial stretch parallel to optical polarisation and (right panel) biaxial uniform stretch with unpolarised light. The discrepancy in intensity is due to the curved film on the lens surface. Adapted from Ref. ²⁶¹, with the permission of AIP Publishing. (D) An aqueous phase containing AuNPs and a heavy metal ion target analyte (*e.g.*, Hg²⁺) are placed in contact with an oil phase containing a dissolved polyaromatic ligand (PAL). Shaking creates a biphasic emulsion, causing all aqueous and organic species present to self-assemble at the common liquid-liquid interface. After assembly, Hg²⁺ can be detected sensitively by SERS through its effects on the *in situ* SERS signals from the PAL molecules attached to the AuNPs surface adsorbed at the interface. Adapted with permission from Ref. ²⁷⁴. Copyright 2014 Wiley-VCH.

In this perspective section, we denote experiments that combine an external manipulation of $\Delta_o^w \phi$ with a potentiostat and simultaneous SERS measurements *in situ* at the ITIES as EC-SERS@ITIES. The only report to date of EC-SERS@ITIES is that by Booth *et al.*²⁷⁶ In that study, citrate stabilised AgNPs were reversibly adsorbed and desorbed from the ITIES for a finite number of cycles by varying $\Delta_o^w \phi$ negatively and positively, respectively. Upon AgNP adsorption at negative potentials a sharp increase in the SERS intensity of the lipophilic organic cation BA⁺ was detected. This observation corresponds very well with that by Bera *et al.*¹⁸ (described *vide supra*) of organic counter-ion condensation onto highly charged AuNPs overcoming the electrostatic barrier presented by the low permittivity organic material at the ITIES during potential-induced adsorption events. Thus, EC-SERS@ITIES can be used to sensitively detect organic ions of opposite charge to the stabilising ligand on interfacially adsorbed plasmonic NPs.

Many other possibilities of EC-SERS@ITIES have yet to be explored. For example, certain charged species (*i.e.*, ions) in either the aqueous or organic phase can be transferred reversibly over and back across the ITIES by varying $\Delta_o^w \phi$. Each ion will undergo IT at a signature formal ion transfer potential ($\Delta_o^w \phi^0$) that is a measure of the Gibbs energy of transfer for that ion expressed on the voltage scale and depends heavily on the charge and chemical structure of the ion.²³ Thus, certain ions in a mixture can be selectively transferred over and back across the ITIES by matching the applied $\Delta_o^w \phi$ with the $\Delta_o^w \phi^0$ for that ion. Therefore, in theory, the SERS signal for the selected ion undergoing IT will be transiently enhanced as it traverses the ITIES through the hot-spots between interfacial AuNPs in the floating gold nanofilms. Indeed, Smirnov *et al.* have demonstrated that the presence of an interfacial gold nanofilm does not impede IT for model ions such as tetramethylammonium cations (TMA⁺).²⁰ Further strategies may be explored that combine the demonstrated ability to achieve electrocatalysis at gold nanofilms with the plasmonic

enhancement at the hot-spots between the AuNPs. For example, the redox active dye Nile Blue is a very popular probe in EC-SERS studies as its oxidised form undergoes resonant excitation at 633 nm, giving a strong SERS signal, but its reduced form is non-resonant leading to a weak SERS signal.²⁵⁵ Thus, the oxidised and reduced forms of this species are readily distinguishable by SERS. As a proof-of-concept, the analogous EC-SERS@ITIES experiment may involve the reduction of the oxidised form of Nile Blue in the aqueous phase *via* AuNP mediated IET from an electron donor species in the oil phase (such as DMFc). The thermodynamics of IET would be controlled by external application of $\Delta_o^w \phi$ by the potentiostat and the disappearance of the oxidised dye signal monitored *in situ* by SERS.

6.2. Electrovariable optics

As noted in section 3.3, to date, only one study has been published that demonstrates clearly the experimental observation of reversible adsorption/desorption of gold nanofilms composed of relatively large AuNPs (*e.g.*, in the size range of 10 to 60 nm) by tuning $\Delta_o^w \phi$.²² However, there are several examples of the reversible stimulus-induced self-assembly of NPs on 2-D interfaces. Sashuk *et al.* reported the dynamic self-assembly of amphiphilic and uncharged NPs dispersed at an air-water interface in response to changes in the gradient of $\gamma_{w/o}$.²⁷⁷ The gradient was changed by either adding or removing organic solvent on the fluid interface, causing the NPs to compress into local dense spots. Once the gradient of $\gamma_{w/o}$ dissipated, the compressed AuNPs disassembled.²⁷⁷ Ding *et al.* dynamically tuned the distance between the AuNPs in a floating gold nanofilm (and hence the nanofilm's optical properties) by rapid, repeatable expansion and contraction of PNIPAM nanocoatings on the AuNPs at different temperatures.⁸⁶ Meanwhile, as discussed, Bera *et al.* have definitively shown that the dynamic lateral movement of AuNPs at the interface is possible by tuning $\Delta_o^w \phi$,¹⁸ a much more convenient external stimulus to employ in possible electrovariable optical devices than the introduction/removal of solvent or varying temperature.

Recently, Gschwend *et al.* have created so called “electrovariable Marangoni shutters”.¹⁷ The concept harnesses known changes in $\gamma_{w/o}$ that can be reversibly induced at the liquid-liquid interface as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$ in the presence of an anionic surfactant (sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS)) that undergoes IT. The interplay of adsorption-desorption and IT as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$ causes instabilities or Marangoni-type movements (*i.e.*, mass transfer along an interface between

two fluids due to a surface tension gradient).^{278–280} The AuNPs in the gold nanofilm are swept up in these Marangoni-type movements, always moving to regions of higher $\gamma_{w/o}$. Indeed, the AuNPs may be induced to either reversibly crowd around the periphery of the interface (leading to the shutter being “off” with the majority of the interface non-reflective) or spread uniformly across the interface (leading to the shutter being “on” and the interface highly reflective) as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$,¹⁷ see **Fig. 15**. The distribution of the electric field at the ITIES is critically dependent on the shape and position of the Pt CEs on either side of the liquid-liquid interface. As a result, by manipulating the latter, further enhanced control over the spatial regions on the interface where the Marangoni-effects are felt strongest, and thus where the AuNPs can be induced to assemble more densely, will be possible.

Fig. 15. Electrovariable Marangoni shutters with floating gold nanofilms at the ITIES. (A) Silanised four-electrode electrochemical cell in a quartz rectangular cuvette with large Pt-mesh aqueous and organic CEs, and an extremely flat and smooth water-TFT interface (critical for reflectance measurements). (B) Monitoring the intensity of light reflected from the centre of a water-TFT interface (black line) as a function of $\Delta_o^w \phi$, varied by cyclic voltammetry (CV; red line). The light was incident on the water-TFT interface at 66° , *i.e.*, below the critical angle for total internal reflection (TIR). The black star on the CV represents a positive $\Delta_o^w \phi$, with the current increasing at this point positively due to the transfer of residual metal cations to the oil phase. After this point $\Delta_o^w \phi$ was scanned to more negative values, immediately causing a dip in the current negatively as metal cations transferred back from the oil into the water phase. The blue and pink stars represent two progressively more negative potentials in the middle of the PPW as $\Delta_o^w \phi$ was scanned negatively. At very positive $\Delta_o^w \phi$ and at $\Delta_o^w \phi$ values spanning the centre of the PPW (*i.e.*, the region between the black and pink stars), the AuNPs were seen to be distributed around the perimeter of the quartz cuvette. Thus, a low reflectance was measured in this potential range (also seen by eye in a video snapshot, bottom-left image). Once $\Delta_o^w \phi$ was scanned to a very negative value (red star), the anionic surfactant SDS transferred from the water to oil phase leading to a large negative increase in current. Immediately, AuNPs were seen to migrate to the centre of the

water-oil interface, rapidly accumulating and causing a huge increase in reflectance (seen by eye in top-right image). Once more, after this point $\Delta_o^w \phi$ was switched in the positive direction causing the SDS to move from back from the oil to water phase, producing a positive current. The increased reflectance was maintained until all SDS ions were transferred back into the water phase (yellow star). Finally, as $\Delta_o^w \phi$ was scanned positively to $\Delta_o^w \phi$ values once more in the centre of the PPW (dark red star), the system returned to its initial state with the AuNPs again crowded around the periphery of the quartz cuvette and the reflectance greatly diminished (seen by eye in bottom-right image). Adapted from Ref. ¹⁷ with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

A major factor when designing electrovariable optics based on dynamic self-assembly of NPs will be response time to the external stimulus (*i.e.*, the applied electric field especially, but also perhaps temperature or light).¹³⁴ With regard to the reversible adsorption and desorption of gold nanofilms from the ITIES, the response time will be limited by the rate of diffusion of AuNPs in the bulk liquid towards the interface and back-off again. Thus, the time-constant for observable “on/off” behaviour could be tens of minutes depending on the concentration and diffusion coefficient of the AuNPs in the bulk phase, and their size.¹³⁴ Such response times may be suitable for niche applications, *e.g.*, windows in large buildings that gradually become more or less reflective to help equalise the temperature at a desired level as the intensity of sunlight rises and drops during the day. Realistically, however, for more general applications the time-constant for observable “on/off” behaviour needs to be reduced to second or ideally millisecond regimes. In this regard, the near instantaneous “on/off” behaviour observed by Gschwend *et al.*¹⁷ for lateral movement of the AuNPs across the fluidic interface is hugely encouraging. Thus, building on this initial premise of combining interfacial gold nanofilms and charged surfactant at an ITIES, rapid response electrovariable optics for mirror and filters applications will be within reach in the short-term.

A more traditional approach has been to deposit a nanofilm on a solid transparent conductive electrode to obtain a mirror, and then strip the metal to obtain a window.²⁸¹ In this case, 100 s was required to obtain 90% of the maximum reflectance for an optimised system.²⁸² Another approach for decreasing the time constant for electro-tuneable reflecting nanoshutters was recently proposed by Kornyshev *et al.*,¹³⁴ who showed theoretically that fast switching within sub-second timescales from mirror to window could be obtained by electrically induced rotation of 2-D arrays of nanocuboids tethered to a transparent conductive electrode.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

To conclude, the practical utility of floating gold nanofilms is already being realised in the analytical chemistry community for SERS sensor applications. However, approaches to date have broadly been limited in scope to using liquid-liquid interfaces for bottom-up self-assembly purposes only. Major advances in SERS and SPR sensors can be made by simultaneously harnessing the aspects of AuNP self-assembly and controllably applying electric fields at the gold nanofilm functionalised ITIES. In this way, for example, the electrocatalytic properties of AuNPs can be utilised in conjunction with their nanoplasmonic properties to create truly unique sensors in a new branch of SERS we call EC-SERS@ITIES. Immediate applications of floating gold nanofilms in rapid response electrovariable optic devices are now within reach thanks to pioneering simulation studies and recent experimental breakthroughs.

To fully realise the potential of functionalising ITIES with nanomaterials some fundamental scientific questions and practical considerations remain to be addressed.²⁸³ For example, precisely where at the water-oil interface is the potential drop located? To describe the electrovariable assembly of nanomaterials at the ITIES, can we develop a combined theory of the interplay of forces on nanomaterials at the ITIES as a function of the strength and polarity of an applied electric field?²⁸³ Currently, experimental observations of electrovariable NP assembly/disassembly at the ITIES are primarily described with empirical rules and formulae. The realisation of such a combined theory would have major implications for the development of smart window technology in particular. Can we develop new techniques to probe the three-phase contact angles of interfacial adsorbed NPs less than 100 nm in size *in situ* at the ITIES? Although several techniques are now available in this regard, as described in Section 4.2, greater resolution of the three-phase contact angle *in situ* at the ITIES remains a challenge. The relative influences of the plasmonic and electrocatalytic properties of gold nanofilms at the ITIES on photo-induced electron transfer events remains an open question, as described in Section 5.4. If fully understood, can the plasmonic features of gold nanofilms be harnessed to develop efficient solar energy conversion devices based on the interaction of AuNP nanofilms at the ITIES and light-absorbing species such as porphyrins? Finally, while this review is limited to discussing mainly simple round-shaped AuNPs, the potential utility and impact of ITIES functionalised with gold (or any other metal) nanorods, nanotriangles, nanocubes, core-shell NPs, Janus NPs, carbon supported NPs, semiconductors *etc.*, for

electrocatalytic, nanoplasmonic and electrovariable optic applications has barely been scratched and represents an exciting research avenue for the future.

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Evgeny Smirnov was born in Tver, Russia. He received his M.Sc. degree from Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia, with emphasis on materials chemistry in 2011. He did his doctoral studies devoted to self-assembly of nanoparticles at liquid-liquid interfaces in Laboratory of Physical and Analytical Electrochemistry at EPFL, Switzerland, and successfully defended his Ph.D. degree in 2017. His scientific interests are mainly focused on the topic of settling gold nanoparticles at various liquid-liquid interfaces, investigating the properties of such nanoparticle assemblies and implementing them for redox catalysis at interfaces as well as for biphasic analyte detection in Raman spectroscopy.

T. Jane Stockmann received her PhD in 2013 under Pr. Zhifeng Ding at Western University in Canada. She then moved to Switzerland to the group of Pr. Hubert Girault at EPFL as a post-doctoral fellow, and performed numerical evaluations of O₂ reduction at soft interfaces. She is currently in France in the group of Drs. Fred Kanoufi and Catherine Combellas as a post-doctoral fellow, where she has been working to characterise oscillating reactions using SECM, ensemble nanoparticle detection for biosensor applications, and single nanoparticle detection at soft interfaces, as well as develop novel nano-composite materials through a Horizon 2020 Marie-Skłodowska Curie Action.

Dr. Pekka Peljo is a group leader and SNSF Ambizione Energy grant holder at the Laboratoire d'Electrochimie Physique et Analytique (LEPA), EPFL, Switzerland since 2016. He received his D.Sc. (Tech.) in 2013 from Aalto University, Finland, under supervision of Prof. Kyösti Kontturi, and has worked as a postdoctoral researcher at LEPA (2013-2016). His research interests currently include non-aqueous redox flow batteries, electrochemistry at soft interfaces and understanding of fundamental theoretical electrochemistry based on thermodynamics.

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Abbreviations

AFM = atomic force microscopy

Ag/AgCl = silver/silver chloride

AgNP = silver nanoparticle

AuNP = gold nanoparticle

AVS = absolute vacuum scale

BA⁺ = bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium cations

BATB = bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate

BiVO₄ = bismuth vanadate

CE = counter electrode

CNT = carbon nanotube

DCB = 1,2-dichlorobenzene

DCE = 1,2-dichloroethane

DDT = 1-dodecanethiol

DMFc = decamethylferrocene

DTBE = 2,2'-dithiobis[1-(2-bromo-2-methyl-propionyloxy)ethane]

ϵ = relative permittivity

EC-SERS = electrochemical surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy

EC-SERS@ITIES = electrochemical surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy *in situ* at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions

E_F^{NP} = Fermi level of the electrons in a single gold nanoparticle within a gold nanofilm

EP = epinephrine

ET-IT = electron transfer-ion transfer

Fc = ferrocene

$[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ = ferri/ferrocyanide

FIT = facilitated ion transfer

(FreSCa) cryo-SEM = freeze-fracture shadow casting cryogenic scanning electron microscopy

FTDT = finite difference time domain

$\gamma_{\text{w/o}}$ = interfacial energy of the water-organic solvent interface

$\gamma_{\text{NP/w}}$ = interfacial energy of the NP-aqueous phase interface

$\gamma_{\text{NP/o}}$ = interfacial energy of the NP-organic solvent interface

GIXRD = grazing incidence X-ray diffraction

GISAXS = grazing-incidence small angle x-ray scattering

HER = hydrogen evolution reaction

IET = interfacial electron transfer

IT = ion transfer

ITIES = interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions

k_{app}^0 = apparent standard ion transfer constant

LC-TEM = liquid cell transmission electron microscopy

LSPR = localised surface plasmon resonance

MD = molecular dynamics

MDDA = 12-mercaptododecanoic acid

MPC = monolayer protected cluster

NP = nanoparticle

ORR = oxygen reduction reaction

PAL = polyaromatic ligand

PC = propylene carbonate

PDMS = polydimethylsiloxane

PIET = photo-induced interfacial electron transfer

PNIPAM = poly-N-isopropylacrylamide

PPW = polarisable potential window

$\Delta_o^w \phi$ = interfacial Galvani potential difference

$\Delta_o^w \phi^{0'}$ = formal ion transfer potential

QELS = quasi-elastic light scattering

RE = reference electrode

σ = surface charge density

SAXS = small angle x-ray scattering

SDS = sodium dodecyl sulfate

SECM = scanning electrochemical microscopy

SERS = surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy

SERRS = surface-enhanced resonance Raman spectroscopy

SEM = scanning electron microscopy

SHE = standard hydrogen electrode

SPC = surface plasmon coupling

SPM = scanning probe microscopy

SPR = surface plasmon resonance

SSHG = surface second harmonic generation

STM = scanning tunneling microscopy

θ = surface coverage

θ_0 = three-phase contact angle of the nanoparticle at the water-oil interface

θ_{SPR} = surface plasmon resonance angle

TB^- = tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate anions

TBA^+ = tetrabutylammonium cations

TBATPB = tetrabutylammonium tetraphenylborate

TEM = transmission electron microscopy

TFT = α,α,α -trifluorotoluene

TIR = total internal reflection

TMA^+ = tetramethylammonium cations

TPB^- = tetraphenylborate anions

TR-SSHG = time-resolved surface second harmonic generation

UV-Vis-NIR = ultraviolet-visible-near infrared

W_{cap} = capillary forces

W_{line} = line tension

W_{solv} = solvation energy

W_{sum} = overall energy profile

WOR = water oxidation reaction

Z_{AuNP} = excess of charge on the gold nanoparticle

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